

an aromatic ring (2.28 δ , 3H, S); aromatic protons at C₆ and C₇ (7.2 δ , m, W.H. 22 c/s); aromatic proton at C₈ (7.7 δ , d with J = 7.5 c/s) which shows further allylic coupling with the proton at C₆ (J = 2.5 c/s). (Found: C, 82.60; H, 8.5. C₂₁H₁₄O requires: C, 82.72; H, 8.10%).

3 : 5-Dimethyl-1-Naphthol (X): The tetralone (IX, 1.0 g, 0.006 M) was dehydrogenated with Pd/c (0.4 g) for 2 hr at 310°-20°. After the reaction was complete, the residue (800 mg) was extracted with ether. The ether extract was then thoroughly extracted with aqueous NaOH solution (10%). The alkaline extract was once washed with ether and then acidified by dilute HCl (10%). The acidified solution on extraction with ether and processing as usual gave crude naphthol, m.p. 82°-83°, yield: 290 mg (29%). The crude naphthol was purified by repeated sublimation and finally crystallised from p.e. (40°-50°) to give colourless crystals, m.p. 101°-102°; yield: 100 mg (10%) $\lambda_{max}^{Ethanol}$ 326 (sh), 313 (sh), 298 and 225 nm [log ϵ , 3.76, 4.00, 4.14 and 4.87]; ν_{max}^{KBr} : 3400, 1408, 1277, 1242, 1147, 1031, 885, 862, 847, 813, 806 and 757. PMR spectrum: Two Ar-CH₃ (2.43 and 2.6 δ , 3H, S, each) phenolic -OH (5.2 δ , 1H, exchangeable) and aromatic protons (6.5-7.86 δ , 5H, complex m). (Found: C, 83.28; H, 7.32. C₁₂H₁₂O requires: C, 83.69; H, 7.02%). It gave a picrate, m.p. 90°-91° and a TNB adduct, m.p. 116.5°. For TNB adduct (Found: N, 9.78. C₁₉H₁₅O₉N₃ requires: N, 9.79%).

Acknowledgement

The author is grateful to Dr. Sukh Dev for his guidance, to Dr. V. S. Pansare and his colleagues for microanalyses, to Shri G. Samuel for NMR and to Dr. (Miss) P. K. Gokhale for IR spectra.

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Reactions of Borazine

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Manuscript received 29 March 19 ; accepted 26 June 1973

BORAZINE trimers have been used as insecticides¹, fungicides, antiseptics², pesticides^{3,4}, plasticizers⁵, and polymer catalyst⁶. The borazine trimer of the type [5H, 12H, 19H, tris, (1,3,2 benzo diazaborolo)] borazine, has been prepared either by refluxing *o*-phenylenediamine and alkyl borates (methyl, ethyl, *iso*-propyl) with⁷ or without⁸ solvent or pyrolysing the complex^{9,10} obtained from the reaction of *o*-phenylenediamine and borontrichloride.

This is claimed to be thermally^{11,1} and hydrolytically stable^{7,12,13}. Gerrard and co-workers¹⁴ obtained from *o*-phenylenediamine and borontrichloride, an insoluble, and infusible polymer, non resistant to hydrolysis. Hohnstedt and Pellicciotto¹⁵ reported the formation of 2-chloroborobenzimidazole from *o*-phenylenediamine dihydrochloride and borontrichloride. Boron polymers¹⁶, obtained from boronalkyls and phenyl-*iso*-nitrile, remained unchanged even when refluxed with mineral acid or base.

The controversial reports about the interaction of *o*-phenylenediamine and borontrichloride^{14,15,17} and the hydrolytical stability of the polymer have prompted to undertake reinvestigations.

The polymer was obtained (68%) when *o*-phenylenediamine and *n*-tributylborate were refluxed for 30 hrs. The use of solvent or extended period of heating, did not increase the yield. The present results indicate that the complex obtained from *o*-phenylenediamine and borontrichloride on heating under reflux in chlorobenzene afforded, polymer devoid of halogen.

The polymer is stable for hydrolysis and was not cleaved with primary amines, similar to simple borazine polymer¹⁰. The cleavage of the polymer with dilute hydrochloric acid or glacial acetic acid to produce *o*-phenylenediamine or its derivative (diacetyl) and boric acid confirms the earlier reports^{8,18}. The formation of 2-methylbenzimidazole should be due to cyclization of diacetyl-*o*-phenylenediamine on being refluxed in glacial acetic acid¹⁹, which would not be possible in case of dilute acetic acid. The cleavage of polymer with alcohol, saturated with hydrogen chloride, to yield *o*-phenylenediamine dihydrochloride might be, due to availability of proton from the solvent which enables the cleavage by hydrogen chloride and thus it differs from the action of hydrogen chloride in non ionic solvent. *o*-Phenylenediamine, initially formed, was converted to its hydrochloride.

Boric acid, did not react with *o*-phenylenediamine even in presence of glycerol which increases its acidity and is in agreement with the previous results.²¹

Experimental

Alkyl borates were prepared by known procedures. The estimation of, chlorine was carried out by Volhard's method, whereas those of N and B by Rittners and Culimo's.²⁰

Borazine Polymer: *o*-Phenylenediamine (21.6 g; 0.2 mole) and *n*-tributylborate (46.0 g; 0.2 mole) were mixed and heated under reflux on an oil bath for 24 hr. The reaction mixture distilled off under reduced pressure, afforded unreacted *n*-tributylborate (6.71 g; 14.8%), *o*-phenylenediamine (2.81 g; 13.0%) and pale yellow residue washed with alcohol (14.75 g; 68.7%), insoluble in ether, benzene, chloroform, etc. but soluble in acetone, m.p. > 320° (Found: N, 24.7; B, 10.04. C₁₈H₁₅N₆B₃ requires: N, 24.14; B, 9.48%).

An azeotropic distillation for 8 hr of *o*-phenylenediamine (5.4 g; 0.05 mole), tributyl borate (11.5 g; 0.05 mole) and xylene (50 ml), and working up the residue as above, after the removal of the solvent and unreacted reactants, gave a yellowish residue of polymer (1.8 g; 11%), m.p. > 320°. (Found: N, 24.25; B, 10.14. C₁₈H₁₅N₆B₃ requires: N, 24.14; B, 9.48%).

A brownish polymer m.p. > 320° was obtained in 40-45% yield, on heating under reflux for 12 hr, *o*-phenylenediamine (5.4; 0.05 mole) and tri-*n*-propyl borate or tri-*iso*-propyl borate with or without xylene.

Polymer from *o*-phenylenediamine HCl. and borontrichloride:

The complex, m.p. 250° (6.4 g;; 79.41%) was obtained by the interaction of borontrichloride (4.2 g; 0.013 mole) and *o*-phenylenediamine dihydrochloride (6.47 g; 0.013 mole) at -20° in chlorobenzene. On heating under reflux in the same solvent in presence of nitrogen, it lost hydrogen chloride over a period as shown in the Table I and afforded the polymer (3.2 g; 50%), colourless, m.p. > 320°. (Found N, 24.30; B, 10.10. calc for C₁₈H₁₅N₆B₃, N, 24.14; B, 9.48%). It was insoluble in organic solvents except acetone.

TABLE I

Sl. No.	Period	% HCl evolved
1.	4 hours	43.44
2.	8 "	4.70
3.	16 "	2.82
4.	24 "	1.566
5.	38 "	0.824

Reaction of Polymer with:

(a) **Water:** An unchanged product in quantitative yield (0.95 g.) was recovered when the polymer (1.0 g.) was heated under reflux with water for 8 hr.

(b) **Acetic acid:** The polymer (1.0 g.) refluxed with acetic acid (5 ml) for 5 hr gave 2-methylbenzimidazole, m.p. 176°, (0.87 g; 86%), on neutralization with sodium acetate and extraction with ether. It did not depress the m.p. of an authentic sample.

(c) **Acetic acid (1.5%):** The polymer (0.5 g) was heated under reflux with acetic acid (5 ml) for 4 hr, filtered off, cooled and neutralized with sodium bicarbonate. *o*-Phenylenediamine (0.32 g; 64%), m.p. 100°, which did not depress the m.p. of an authentic sample, was obtained.

(d) **Hydrochloric acid:** The polymer (0.4 g.) and hydrochloric acid (10 ml) were mixed and refluxed for 5 hr. The clear solution on neutralization with cold ammonium hydroxide yielded *o*-phenylenediamine (0.25 g; 62.5%), m.p. 100°-01°.

(e) **Alcohol, saturated with hydrogen chloride:** The polymer (0.5 g) was heated under reflux for 4 hr, with an alcohol (15 ml.), saturated with hydrogen chloride. The reaction mixture was filtered off, the filtrate concentrated and on being allowed to stand gave *o*-phenylenediamine dihydrochloride (0.62 g; 97.47%), m.p. 251°-52°, mix m.p. with an authentic sample was 252°.

(f) ***p*-Toluidine:** The polymer (2.0 g; 0.00575 mole) and *p*-toluidine (1.85 g; 0.00575 mole) were taken in benzene (50 ml) and refluxed for 8 hr. The

residue, (1.0 g) remained, after distilling off the solvent, washed with ether, was found to be unreacted polymer while ethereal washings afforded *p*-toluidine (1.80 g.).

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Estimation of Free Sulphur by Amperometry

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Manuscript received 29 March 1973; accepted 26 June 1973

ONE of the most widely used method for the determination of free sulphur in vulcanized rubber is the sulphite method originally developed by Bolotnikov and Gurova¹. The method is based

on the reaction between sulphur and an aqueous solution of sodium sulphite to form sodium thio-sulphate which is estimated by volumetric titration with standardized iodine after removing the unreacted excess sodium sulphite with formalin. Sulphur-bearing accelerators interfered with the results and Oldham, Baker and Craytor² modified the method so that it remains valid in presence of the common accelerators like mercaptobenzothiazole (MBT) by precipitating out the latter as cadmium salt before carrying out the titration of the thio-sulphate. The method recommended by ASTM³ is based on Oldham's modification. In the present paper we investigated the suitability of the amperometric titration method for the estimation of the thiosulphate formed from sulphur under the above experimental conditions.

The procedure of Oldham *et al.*² was followed except for the titration step. Known amounts of sulphur (6 mg downwards) were boiled with 100 ml of 5% sodium sulphite solution for 2 hr in presence of 5 ml of 1% sodium stearate suspension and 1 g of paraffin wax. 100 ml of 0.5% strontium chloride were then added to precipitate fatty acids followed by 10 ml of 3% cadmium acetate to precipitate mercaptobenzothiazole which might be present in the actual rubber vulcanizate. In other words the experimental conditions were maintained exactly the same as in the actual analysis of rubber vulcanizates. The solution was then filtered into a 500 ml volumetric flask and treated with 5 ml of 40% formalin solution and 12 ml of glacial acetic acid. The volume was then made upto the mark and 50 ml aliquots were taken for amperometric titration of the thio-sulphate with iodine using a rotating platinum wire electrode and a standard saturated calomel electrode. The results are reported in Table 1.

TABLE I—AMPEROMETRIC ESTIMATION OF SULPHUR BY
SULPHITE DIGESTION USING IODINE SOLUTION

Sulphur taken (mg)	Strength of iodine soln. used	Sulphur found (mg)	Deviation (%)
6.046	$0.464 \times 10^{-2}N$	6.054	+0.13
6.046	"	6.069	+0.21
3.032	"	3.034	+0.06
3.032	"	3.034	+0.06
0.302	$0.464 \times 10^{-3}N$	0.298	-1.32
0.302	"	0.299	-0.99
0.151	"	0.141	-6.60
0.151	"	0.141	-6.60

It can be seen that free sulphur can be estimated very accurately even when present in amounts as low as 3×10^{-4} g by amperometric titration of the thiosulphate formed by sulphite digestion. Vogel⁴ has recommended the use of a supporting electrolyte which is 0.1 M in potassium chloride and 0.004 M in potassium iodide for amperometric titration of thiosulphate with iodine. We have found that this